

leaf stages tested. The 1.5–2.0-leaf stage was the growth stage most susceptible to DM (100% DI), with a mortality of 70.7–75.2%. The percentage leaf area damage (LAD, excluding dead plants) on seedlings caused by both fungi was not as high as expected. EM and DM significantly inhibited the height of barnyardgrass seedlings at different leaf stages. Other experiments have indicated that LAD and mortality rates were positively correlated with inoculum dose and duration of the dew period after inoculation.

Under greenhouse conditions and when applied at an inoculum dose of 5.0×10^7 conidia

m^{-2} , EM and DM were not pathogenic to rice seedlings (including indica, japonica, and hybrid rice) and to most other crops tested (Table 2). However, sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) was susceptible to EM and slightly susceptible to DM, and maize (*Zea mays*) was also slightly susceptible to EM. Barnyardgrass was the only plant species highly susceptible to these fungi, with EM causing plant death.

Preliminary results indicated the potential of DM and EM pathogens in controlling barnyardgrass, but further research is required to assess the risks to nontarget plant species

and to evaluate performance under field conditions.

References

- Holm LG, Plucknett DL, Pancho JV, Herberger JP. 1977. The world's worst weeds: distribution and biology. Honolulu, Hawaii. (USA): The University Press of Hawaii.
- Huang S, Yu L, Watson AK. 1999. Study of conidia production characterization of barnyardgrass fungi *Alternaria alternata* and *Curvularia lunata*. In: Proceedings of the 6th Weed Science Conference of China, 19-21 Mar 1999, Nanning, China. p 165–169.
- Zhang WM, Moody K, Watson AK. 1996. Responses of *Echinochloa* species and rice (*Oryza sativa*) to indigenous pathogenic fungi. Plant Dis. 80(9):1053–1058.

Table 2. Susceptibility of selected crop plants to potential biological control fungi of barnyardgrass.^a

Crop	EM	DM	Control	Crop	EM	DM	Control
<i>Zea mays</i>	ls	ns	ns	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	ns	ns	ns
<i>Glycine max</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>Brassica napus oleifera</i>	ns	ns	ns
<i>Vigna sesquipedalis</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>Oryza sativa</i> Jiayu 293 (indica)	ns	ns	ns
<i>Vicia faba</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>O. sativa</i> Xiushui II (japonica)	ns	ns	ns
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	s	ls	ns	<i>O. sativa</i> Xieyou 46 (hybrid rice)	ns	ns	ns
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	ns	ns	ns	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	d	hs	ns

^ans = not susceptible; ls = lightly susceptible, with a few and small lesions on leaves; s = susceptible; hs = highly susceptible with many and expanded lesions on the leaves; d = dead plant. EM = *Exserohilum monoceras*, DM = *Drechslera monoceras*.

Response of two rice cultivars to competition from *Echinochloa crus-galli*

S. Pheng, School of Land and Food, University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Queensland 4072, Australia; G.C. Jahn, IRRI; and B. Khiev and C. Pol, Crop Protection Program, Cambodian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (CARDI), P.O. Box 01, Phnom Penh, Cambodia E-mail: s800661@student.uq.edu.au, g.jahn@cgiar.com, kbunnarith@bigpond.com.kh

Barnyardgrass [*Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv.] is an important weed of rice in irrigated and rainfed ecosystems in Cambodia. Rice yields decrease as barnyardgrass populations increase (Smith 1968). To minimize weed competition, Cambodian farmers transplant rice and practice hand-weeding (Jahn et al

1997). The success of this method depends on the amount of standing water after transplanting and the critical period of weeding. Unpredictable rainfall does not favor the use of water in weed management. In addition, labor for hand-weeding is becoming scarce because of competition from other industries. Although

herbicides can be used as a labor-saving option, they are expensive and may cause health and environmental hazards if incorrectly applied. In low-input farming systems such as those in Cambodia, competitive rice cultivars may be an important part of weed management.

An experiment was conducted from September 1997 to January 1998 in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, to determine the competitive abilities of two rice cultivars, IR66 and CAR8 against different weed densities. The experiment consisted of six treatments resulting from the possible combination of varieties IR66 and CAR8, and three densities of barnyardgrass (0, 20, and 40 kg ha⁻¹). The experiment, conducted under rainfed conditions, used a randomized complete block design with five replications.

IR66, a modern rice cultivar, is early maturing. It has short stems and short, narrow leaves, whereas CAR8 has long stems and large leaf areas (Table 1). CAR8 is a Cambodian traditional rice cultivar selected for purity by the Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP). IR66 required only 66 d to complete the vegetative growth stage, while CAR8 re-

quired 112 d. The analysis of variance indicated that CAR8 had significantly higher yields than IR66. Partitioning of sum of squares (PSS) indicated that the rice yield of both cultivars decreased linearly when weed density increased (Table 2). However, IR66 was more susceptible to weed competition than CAR8. When the weed-seeding rate was increased to 20 kg ha⁻¹, the average yield of IR66 decreased by 71% compared with a yield reduction of 37% for CAR8. When the weed-seeding rate was increased to 40 kg ha⁻¹, a rare case of weed infestation, CAR8 still yielded an average of 1.3 t ha.

CAR8 could have outperformed IR66 against *E. crus-galli* because it possesses competitive traits such as late maturation, longer stems, and droopy leaves (Ampong-Nyarko and De Datta 1991, Smith 1983). In addition, laboratory tests indicated that CAR8 exhibits allelopathic activity, while IR66 does not (Peng et

al 1999). CAR8 is recommended for rainfed lowland areas with high weed infestation. Weed management can be enhanced when competitive cultivars are integrated with other weed management options.

References

- Ampong-Nyarko K, De Datta SK. 1991. A handbook of weed control in rice. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute.
- Jahn GC, Pheng S, Khiev B, Pol C. 1997. Pest management practices of lowland rice farmers in Cambodia. In: Heong KL, Escalada MM, editors. Pest management of rice farmers in Asia. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p 35–51.
- Pheng S, Adkins SW, Olofsson M, Jahn G. 1999. Allelopathic effects of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) on the growth of awnless barnyardgrass [*Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link]: a new form for weed management. Cambodian J. Agric. 2(1):42–49.
- Smith Jr. RJ 1968. Weed competition in rice. Weed Sci. 16:252–254.
- Smith Jr. RJ 1983. Weeds of major economic importance in rice and yield losses due to weed competition. In: Weed control in rice. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p 20–36.

Table 1. Phenological and morphological characteristics of IR66 and CAR8 in monoculture under rainfed conditions without fertilizer, based on average measurements taken from five plants plot⁻¹.

Characteristic	IR66	CAR8
PhenologyTM		
Vegetative stage (d)	66	112
Duration (d)	96	142
Morphology		
Plant height (cm)	78.8	131.7
Leaf length (cm)	30.6	42.0
Leaf width (cm)	0.6	0.7

Table 2. Mean rice yields (t ha⁻¹) of two varieties (IR66 and CAR8) grown at three different densities of *E. crus-galli* seeds.^a

Density (kg ha ⁻¹)	IR66	CAR8
D ₁ (0)	1.1 a	3.5 a
D ₂ (20)	0.3 b	2.2 b
D ₃ (40)	0.3 b	1.3 c

^aMeans within columns followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$, LSD test).

Acknowledgments

We thank the Australian Agency for International Development (AusAID) for financing this research through CIAP. Special thanks go to Mr. K.H. Pith of CIAP for providing us with the germplasm.

